

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21

Enhancing the phosphorus content of layered double hydroxide fertilizers by intercalating polymeric phosphate instead of orthophosphate: a feasibility study

Maarten Everaert^{1*}, Fien Degryse², Mike J. McLaughlin², Simon Smolders³, Ivan Andelkovic², Roslyn Baird²,
Erik Smolders¹

¹ Division of Soil and Water Management, Department of Earth and Environmental Science, KU Leuven,
Kasteelpark Arenberg 20, B-3001 Heverlee, Belgium.

² School of Agriculture, Food and Wine, The University of Adelaide, PMB 1, Waite Campus, Glen
Osmond, SA 5064, Australia.

³ Centre for Membrane Separations, Adsorption, Catalysis and Spectroscopy for Sustainable Solutions
(cMACS), KU Leuven, Celestijnenlaan 200F, 3001 Leuven, Belgium.

* Corresponding author: maarten.everaert@kuleuven.be

ORCID ID:

- Maarten Everaert: 0000-0002-3493-0631
- Fien Degryse: 0000-0002-4875-2944
- Mike J. McLaughlin: 0000-0001-6796-4144
- Simon Smolders: 0000-0002-3622-2022
- Ivan Andelkovic: 0000-0002-4570-0540
- Roslyn Baird: 0000-0002-1269-0323
- Erik Smolders: 0000-0003-3054-2444

22 **Abstract**

23 **Hypothesis:** Layered double hydroxide (LDH) loaded with orthophosphate (PO_4) are suggested as slow-
24 release P fertilizers. However, PO_4 -LDHs have a low maximal P content, related to high charge $\text{HPO}_4^{2-}/\text{PO}_4^{3-}$
25 anions occupying the anion exchange capacity (AEC) of LDHs. We postulate that the P content of LDHs can
26 be enhanced by exchanging them with polymeric-P (*i.e.* trimetaphosphate, P_3O_9), which has a lower molar
27 charge/P ratio than its monomer.

28 **Experiments:** Adsorption capacities were compared between PO_4 and P_3O_9 for as-synthesized and
29 calcined MgAl LDHs with Mg/Al ratio of 2, 3, or 4; the P-LDHs were characterized (XRD, FTIR). Dialysis and
30 soil incubation experiments were performed with PO_4 -LDHs, P_3O_9 -LDHs, and corresponding soluble
31 fertilizers to compare their P release and P solubility (CaCl_2 extract).

32 **Findings:** The P adsorption capacities were 1.25-1.60 fold larger for P_3O_9 compared to PO_4 , yet the high
33 theoretical P contents with P_3O_9 were not achieved (incomplete loading, P_3O_9 depolymerization). P_3O_9 -
34 Mg_3Al released polymeric-P whereas P_3O_9 - Mg_2Al released depolymerized PO_4 , and P release from P_3O_9 -
35 LDHs was slower than that of PO_4 -LDHs. With soil incubation, soluble P from P_3O_9 -LDH was initially lower
36 but later converged to that of PO_4 -LDH as result of continued hydrolysis, yet did not exceed that of the
37 soluble P_3O_9 and PO_4 fertilizers.

38 **Keywords**

39 Layered double hydroxide (LDH), anionic clays, slow-release fertilizer, phosphorus, anion exchange,
40 polyphosphate, trimetaphosphate, calcination

41 1. Introduction

42 Phosphorus (P) is an essential macronutrient for plants, and crop production systems strongly rely on
43 fertilizer P inputs to ensure high crop yields. Currently, global annual P input accounts for 20 Tg, and
44 required P inputs are estimated to further increase during the 21st century as a result of population growth
45 and shifts in consumption patterns [1]. Conventional mineral P fertilizers are typically soluble acidulated
46 products derived from rock phosphate, *e.g.* monoammonium phosphate (MAP), diammonium phosphate
47 (DAP) single superphosphate (SSP) or triple superphosphate (TSP), yet currently there exist several
48 incentives to develop alternative P fertilizer compounds. First, the production of mineral P fertilizers relies
49 on the availability of finite rock phosphate reserves. To carefully and responsibly use of this nonrenewable
50 resource, alternative slow-release P fertilizer compounds can be used to increase the efficiency of P use.
51 With regard to this, it is hypothesized that a sustained supply of P, rather than the immediate dissolution
52 of P from conventional soluble P fertilizers, could be beneficial for crop P acquisition in certain soil
53 conditions. This could be the case in calcareous soils, where high local P concentrations from soluble
54 granular P fertilizers result in the precipitation of poorly-soluble Ca-phosphates [2,3]. Secondly, the rapid
55 dissolution of soluble P fertilizers can cause excessive leaching/runoff of P to groundwater and surface
56 water, if P fertilizer application is improperly managed. Consequently, these P losses could cause
57 eutrophication and contribute to environmental degradation. With the use of slow-release P sources,
58 these risks of P losses to the environment could be significantly reduced.

59 Over the last decade, several material classes have been explored for the development of slow-release P
60 fertilizer compounds, such as recovered P precipitates (*e.g.* struvite) [4], graphene-based materials [5],
61 modified zeolites [6], metal-organic frameworks [7], and engineered biochars [8]. Recently, also layered
62 double hydroxide (LDH) materials were introduced as slow-release fertilizer materials. LDHs are inorganic
63 anion exchange materials that consist of metal hydroxide layers and interlayers of anionic compounds.
64 These materials are often represented by the general formula $[M^{2+}_{1-x} M^{3+}_x (OH)_2]^{x+} [A^{m-}_{x/m}] \cdot nH_2O$, with x

65 the cation isomorphic substitution ratio equal to $M^{3+}/(M^{2+} + M^{3+})$, and A^{m-} the intercalated anion, *e.g.*
66 phosphate (further denoted as PO_4 , a general notation for the different $H_2PO_4^-$, HPO_4^{2-} or PO_4^{3-} species).
67 The reversible nature of the electrostatic anion bonding in LDHs makes these materials particularly
68 interesting as controlled sources of P for plant nutrition, since counter anions from the soil solution (*e.g.*
69 carbonate) can slowly exchange with the anionic nutrient from the LDH. In acid oxide-rich soils, application
70 of PO_4 -LDH fertilizers resulted in high P availability and P uptake [9–11], yet this was likely more a result
71 of the liming effect of LDHs than of their slow-release properties. However, in alkaline/calcareous soils,
72 also promising results were obtained with PO_4 -LDH fertilizers [12], where slow P release could potentially
73 reduce the formation of poorly soluble Ca-phosphates. Furthermore, several studies illustrated the
74 benefits of PO_4 -LDH fertilizers in terms of environmental performance, *e.g.* limiting P leaching and surface
75 runoff with P-LDH application to soil [13,14].

76 Despite the promising results of LDHs as slow-release P fertilizers, the relatively low P content of LDHs
77 remains a major disadvantage for their application as fertilizers. The reported P contents for LDH fertilizers
78 range between 3.8 and 4.2 wt% [10,11,15], which is low in comparison with other slow-release P sources,
79 *e.g.* struvite (7.4-13.4 wt%) [4,16] or with conventional P fertilizers (*e.g.* 20 wt% for TSP). In general, the P
80 content of LDHs is determined by *i)* the AEC of the LDH, which is linked to the M^{2+}/M^{3+} ratio, *ii)* the mass
81 of the LDH matrix, which depends on the choice of metal cations and the water content, and *iii)* the charge
82 of PO_4 anions in the material (*i.e.* monovalent $H_2PO_4^-$, divalent HPO_4^{2-} or trivalent PO_4^{3-}). A higher charge
83 of the adsorbed PO_4 anion decreases the P uptake capacity, and thus also the P content of the obtained
84 LDH. Therefore, P uptake can be maximized by targeting a low molar charge/P ratio for the intercalated
85 PO_4 . For example, a Mg-Al LDH with a molar Mg/Al ratio of 2 could in theory achieve a P content of 11.2
86 wt% if only $H_2PO_4^-$ is taken up via anion exchange (hydrates excluded from calculation), while the
87 theoretical P content is 6.8 wt% with HPO_4^{2-} uptake and 4.9 wt% with PO_4^{3-} uptake. Spectroscopic evidence
88 on PO_4 speciation in Mg-Al LDHs, however, only identified HPO_4^{2-} and PO_4^{3-} as adsorbed PO_4 species in

89 LDHs, and not H_2PO_4^- [11,17,18]. This calculation is in line with the low reported values for the P content
90 of LDH fertilizers (with a PO_4^{3-} speciation).

91 The limitation for H_2PO_4^- intercalation likely arises from the fact that *i)* LDHs have a poor stability in acid
92 conditions [19], which are required to maintain H_2PO_4^- as the dominant PO_4 species in solution and *ii)* LDHs
93 with high anion capacity, and thus high charge density (*i.e.* low $\text{M}^{2+}/\text{M}^{3+}$ ratio), have a higher selectivity
94 towards divalent HPO_4^{2-} or trivalent PO_4^{3-} anions than towards monovalent H_2PO_4^- anions [20].
95 Furthermore, the speciation of PO_4 in the adsorption solution is a poor indicator of the adsorbed PO_4
96 speciation [17] because of different uptake selectivities for the different PO_4 species, the local alkaline
97 character of LDHs and changes in the solution pH during anion exchange in batch conditions.

98 Here, we hypothesize that the P content of LDH fertilizers could be enhanced with the intercalation of
99 polymeric phosphate anions instead of orthophosphate anions. Polyphosphate compounds (*e.g.*
100 tripolyphosphate, further denoted as P_3O_{10}), and particularly cyclic polyphosphate compounds (*e.g.*
101 trimetaphosphate, further denoted as P_3O_9), have an intrinsic low molar charge/P ratio in comparison
102 with PO_4 , even in alkaline conditions. Hence, based on these charge properties, P_3O_{10} and P_3O_9 are
103 promising candidates for the development of P-LDH fertilizers with increased P content. Furthermore,
104 both P_3O_{10} and P_3O_9 are performant P sources for plants, and thus suitable for use as fertilizer P
105 compounds [21]. However, P_3O_{10} can form strong complexes with metal cations [22] and, as a result, the
106 presence of P_3O_{10} can deteriorate the LDH structure [23]. This would cause the precipitation of P_3O_{10}
107 rather than a reversible bonding via anion exchange, and can be undesirable for a fertilizer application.
108 Furthermore, P_3O_{10} has also been shown to be more prone to decomposition (hydrolysis) in aqueous
109 conditions in comparison with P_3O_9 [24]. Consequently, for this study, P_3O_9 was selected as the most
110 suitable candidate for intercalation in LDHs. Hence, we investigated the adsorption of PO_4 and P_3O_9 by as-
111 synthesized and calcined MgAl LDHs with a varying molar Mg/Al ratio and elucidated the P uptake
112 mechanisms. Subsequently, in a simulated alkaline soil solution, the total P (TP) and molybdate-reactive

113 P (MRP) release was determined for LDHs loaded with either PO₄ or P₃O₉. Finally, a PO₄-loaded and a P₃O₉-
114 loaded LDH were applied to a calcareous soil, and the P availability was compared with that of soluble P
115 compounds NaH₂PO₄, KH₂PO₄ and Na₃P₃O₉.

116

117 **2. Materials and methods**

118 **2.1. LDH synthesis and characterization**

119 Three MgAl LDHs were prepared via co-precipitation with a molar Mg/Al ratio of either 2, 3 or 4, termed
120 Mg₂Al, Mg₃Al and Mg₄Al, respectively. Metal solutions with a total metal concentration of 2 M were
121 prepared by dissolving MgCl₂·6H₂O and AlCl₃·6H₂O in MilliQ™ water at the required molar ratios. With a
122 B. Braun Perfusor pump, these metal solutions were added at a rate of 10 mL h⁻¹ to a 200 mL MilliQ™
123 solution. During precipitation in a N₂ atmosphere, the pH was maintained at 10 ± 0.1 with the controlled
124 addition of a 4 M NH₄OH solution with a Metrohm Titrino 702. After the addition of 50 mL metal solution
125 to the synthesis mixture, the material was ripened in the synthesis mixture for 0.5 h at room temperature.
126 Subsequently, the synthesis mixture was ripened at 70 °C for 24 hours. Finally, the materials were
127 recovered by centrifugation, washed three times with MilliQ™ water and dried at 70 °C. To determine the
128 metal content of the LDHs, the dried samples were dissolved in HCl and analyzed with Inductively Coupled
129 Plasma Optical Emission Spectrometry (ICP-OES, PerkinElmer Optima 3300 DV). From the Mg and Al
130 contents of the materials, the isomorphous substitution ratio x and theoretical AEC were calculated using
131 the LDH formula [Mg²⁺_{1-x}Al³⁺_x(OH)₂]^{x+} [Cl⁻_x]. The crystallographic characteristics of the as-synthesized LDHs
132 were investigated with powder x-ray diffraction (XRD), performed on a Malvern PANalytical Empyrean
133 diffractometer in transmission mode, using a PIXcel3D solid state detector and Cu anode (Cu Kα1: 1.5406
134 Å; Cu Kα2: 1.5444 Å). Using Bragg's law, the basal spacing of the LDH was calculated from the position of
135 the (003) reflection in the XRD pattern (uncertainty of 0.0048 Å). The FTIR spectra were obtained with a
136 Varian 620-IR.

137 The as-synthesized Mg_2Al and Mg_3Al LDHs were subjected to calcination in a muffle furnace (Nabertherm
138 L15/11) at either 300, 350, 400, 450 or 500 °C for five hours (ramp 5 °C min⁻¹), and the weight loss from
139 each treatment was recorded. Additionally, the calcination behavior of as-synthesized Mg_2Al and Mg_3Al
140 LDHs was characterized with thermogravimetric analysis (TGA, on a NETZSCH STA 449 F3 Jupiter thermal
141 analyzer) with Pt pan with a 5 °C min⁻¹ heating ramp to 550 °C in an air atmosphere.

142

143 **2.2. Uptake of PO_4 and P_3O_9 by as-synthesized and calcined LDHs**

144 Adsorption isotherms were recorded by loading the three non-calcined LDHs with P using either
145 $NaH_2PO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$ (Sigma-Aldrich, ≥99%) or $Na_3P_3O_9$ (Sigma-Aldrich, ≥95%). For this, solutions with variable
146 total P concentrations between 0 and up to 58 mM (for Mg_2Al), 46 mM (for Mg_3Al) and 38 mM (for Mg_4Al)
147 were prepared from either $NaH_2PO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$ or $Na_3P_3O_9$. The pH of the adsorption solutions was adjusted to
148 pH 7 using a dilute NaOH solution, and a liquid-to-solid ratio (S:L) of 200 L g⁻¹ was used for the reactions.
149 The suspensions were shaken end-over-end for 24 h (0.42 rotations s⁻¹; 20 ± 2 °C). After reaction, the
150 supernatants were recovered by centrifugation (4,000 g, 15 min), and subsequently analyzed for the P
151 concentration (ICP-OES) and the pH. Using the same reaction conditions, the PO_4 and P_3O_9 uptake by
152 calcined Mg_2Al and Mg_3Al LDHs was determined from solutions prepared with either $NaH_2PO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$ or
153 $Na_3P_3O_9$, with a total P concentration of either 23 mM for the calcined Mg_2Al materials or 18 mM for the
154 calcined Mg_3Al materials. All recovered P-loaded LDH materials were dried at 60 °C and a selection was
155 characterized using XRD and FTIR. For the different LDHs, the PO_4 and P_3O_9 uptake relative to the AEC of
156 each material was calculated based on the speciation of adsorbed P (derived from material
157 characterization) and the theoretical AEC of each LDH.

158

159 2.3. Release of PO₄ and P₃O₉ from LDHs

160 The P release kinetics from PO₄ and P₃O₉ loaded LDHs (Mg₂Al and Mg₃Al) were determined and compared
161 to those of soluble references, namely NaH₂PO₄·2H₂O and Na₃P₃O₉ using a method adapted from Dox *et*
162 *al.* [25]. Briefly, this method consists of P desorption by exchanging the P-LDHs with CO₃²⁻ at a large L:S
163 ratio to ensure near-constant CO₃²⁻ concentrations; phase separation is achieved with a dialysis
164 membrane, with the LDH within the membrane bag. To load the LDHs with P, the LDHs were shaken in
165 pH-7 solutions containing either 23 (Mg₂Al) or 18 (Mg₃Al) M P as either NaH₂PO₄·2H₂O or Na₃P₃O₉ (L:S of
166 200 mL g⁻¹, 20 ± 2 °C). The P-loaded materials were recovered by centrifugation (4,000 g, 15 min), briefly
167 rinsed with MilliQ™ water, again recovered by centrifugation and dried at 60 °C. The P-loaded LDHs and
168 the reference salts/fertilizers were transferred to dialysis membranes (Spectra/Por 4; regenerated
169 cellulose; MWCO, 12-14 kDa; diameter, 16 mm) at a total loading of 5 mg P/bag, as well as 5 mL of a 2
170 mM NaHCO₃ solution (pH 8.25). The dialysis membranes with fertilizer materials were added to 950-mL
171 pots containing 925 mL of a 2 mM NaHCO₃ solution (triplicate treatment), which were shaken horizontally.
172 After 1, 3, 8, 24, 48, 96 and 168 h, 3 mL of the outer solutions was sampled, and the P concentrations in
173 the solutions were measured with ICP-OES and with the molybdate-blue colorimetric method. A
174 preliminary test with 0.5-mg P/L solutions indicated that only 3% of P₃O₉ was detected colorimetrically.
175 Comparable values have been reported for the other polymeric phosphates (*e.g.* tripolyphosphate, phytic
176 acid) with malachite-green colorimetry [26]. Thus, analyzing the solutions with both ICP-OES for total P
177 (TP) and colorimetry for molybdate-reactive P (MRP) allowed us to infer the speciation of P desorbed from
178 the P₃O₉-loaded LDHs. After the 168 h period, the dialysis membranes with internal suspension were
179 digested in boiling HNO₃ using a MARS 6 microwave digestion system (*CEM*), and the remaining P was
180 determined with ICP-OES.

181

182 **2.4. Application of LDH loaded with PO₄ or P₃O₉ to a calcareous soil**

183 A calcareous soil was sampled in Isla Mayor (Spain), the properties of which are presented in Table 1.
184 Different powdered P fertilizers were mixed into 180 g dry soil at a rate of 52 mg P kg⁻¹, *i.e.* PO₄-exchanged
185 Mg₃Al LDH, P₃O₉-exchanged Mg₃Al LDH, NaH₂PO₄·2H₂O, KH₂PO₄ and Na₃P₃O₉. Two different soluble PO₄
186 fertilizers, NaH₂PO₄·2H₂O and KH₂PO₄, were included to assess the effect of Na addition on P availability
187 (soil dispersion at elevated Na concentrations). A control treatment without P additions was also included.
188 All treatments were prepared in triplicate. Subsequently, the soils were wetted to field capacity (325 g
189 water kg⁻¹ dry soil) with the addition of deionized water, and were placed in a dark incubation chamber at
190 20 °C. During the incubation, a constant water content of the soil samples was maintained with additions
191 every two days. At specific times during the incubation up to 70 days (1, 3, 7, 14, 21, 35, 49 and 70 days),
192 a sample from the well-mixed incubated soils was taken and extracted for 24 h in a 1 mM CaCl₂ solution
193 at a liquid:solid ratio of 10 mL g⁻¹. After centrifugation and filtration of the supernatant, the
194 molybdate reactive P was determined spectrophotometrically (absorbance at 890 nm using a Perkin-
195 Elmer Lambda 20) and the total P was determined via Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry
196 (Agilent 7700).

197

198 Table 1: Selected physicochemical properties of the calcareous soil.

Site of origin		Isla Mayor, Seville, Spain
Soil type ^a		Vertisol
Clay ^b	(%)	8.3
Silt ^b	(%)	76.16
Sand ^b	(%)	15.52
pH ^c		7.88
CEC ^d	cmol _c kg ⁻¹	26.4
C/N ^e		21.94
Organic C ^e	(%)	1.84
Inorganic C ^e	(%)	2.66
P in soil solution ^f	(μg P L ⁻¹)	10
Fe _{ox} ^g	(g Fe kg ⁻¹)	2.91
Al _{ox} ^g	(g Al kg ⁻¹)	0.72
Mn _{ox} ^g	(g Mn kg ⁻¹)	0.32
P _{ox} ^g	(mg P kg ⁻¹)	3.00
FC ^h	(mL kg ⁻¹)	325
K ⁱ	(L kg ⁻¹)	120
n ⁱ		0.36

199 ^a Major soil groups, IUSS Working Group WRB.

200 ^b Clay, silt, sand and texture class based on particle size distribution determined by laser diffraction method; acidic soil's texture determined by
201 pipette method.

202 ^c pH (1:5, 2 hr) determined in 0.01 M CaCl₂.

203 ^d Cation exchange capacity (CEC) was determined in a 0.0166 M cobalt hexamine (Cohex) extract (ISO, 2007), as the difference between total Co
204 added and Co measured in the extract with ICP-OES.

205 ^e C/N and organic C and inorganic C as % of total soil mass determined by the combustion method.

206 ^f P in soil solution determined by indirect sorption/desorption method (1 mM CaCl₂).

207 ^g Ammonium oxalate extractable Fe, Al, Mn and P [27].

208 ^h Field capacity (FC) determined through the glistening effect.

209 ⁱ Fit parameters for the P sorption isotherms described by the Freundlich equation ($P_{\text{sorbed}} = k (P_{\text{solution}})^n$).

210

211 3. Results and discussion

212 3.1. Characterization of as-synthesized LDHs

213 Phase-pure MgAl LDHs were obtained from the coprecipitation procedure, as shown by the XRD patterns

214 of the materials (Figure S1). The elemental composition of the LDHs indicated that the molar Mg/Al ratios

215 of the materials were only slightly below those of the metal chloride precursor solutions, following a

216 successful coprecipitation of Mg²⁺ and Al³⁺ (Table 1). From this elemental composition and the general

217 LDH formula [Mg²⁺_{1-x} Al³⁺_x (OH)₂]^{x+} [A^{m-}_{x/m}] (excluding hydrates), the theoretical anion exchange capacity

218 (AEC) of the LDHs was calculated, which was 4.73 mmol_c g⁻¹ for Mg₂Al, 3.72 mmol_c g⁻¹ for Mg₃Al and

219 3.20 mmol_c g⁻¹ for Mg₄Al LDH (Table 1). The characteristic (003) reflection in the XRD patterns of the LDHs
220 indicated a decrease in the basal spacing with a decreasing Mg/Al ratio (*i.e.* higher AEC and layer charge
221 density), ranging between 7.68 Å for Mg₂Al and 8.07 Å for Mg₄Al (Figure 1a). The basal spacing equals the
222 sum of the interlayer spacing and the layer thickness, with the latter being a constant value (4.77 Å) [28].
223 Hence, the decrease in the basal spacing with a lower Mg/Al ratio is related to a decrease in the interlayer
224 spacing, with an interlayer spacing of 2.92 Å for the Mg₂Al, 3.17 Å for the Mg₃Al and 3.20 Å for the Mg₄Al
225 LDH (Table 1), which is in agreement with the Cl-MgAl materials obtained by Matusik *et al.* [29]. The
226 smaller interlayer spacing of the Mg₂Al LDH prepared from chloride salts was likely related to the presence
227 of some CO₃²⁻ and/or OH⁻ anions in the interlayer gallery, attracted by the higher layer charge density of
228 this material. The FTIR spectrum of the Mg₂Al LDH showed bands at 1365 and 873 cm⁻¹, which were
229 attributed to CO₃²⁻ (Figure 1b) [30]. Furthermore, for the three as-synthesized LDHs, characteristic IR
230 bands for LDHs were shown, such as the bending mode of interlayer water/hydroxides at 1631 cm⁻¹, the
231 Al-OH deformation band at 945 cm⁻¹ and the Mg-OH translation mode at 635 cm⁻¹ [31].

232 Table 2: Material properties of the Mg₂Al, Mg₃Al and Mg₄Al LDHs.

Material	Molar Mg ²⁺ /Al ³⁺ ratio in synthesis solution	Molar Mg ²⁺ /Al ³⁺ ratio in LDHs	Isomorphous substitution ratio x	Theoretical AEC <i>mmol_c g⁻¹</i>	Mg content <i>wt%</i>	Al content <i>wt%</i>	Basal spacing <i>Å</i>	Interlayer spacing <i>Å</i>
-	-	-	-	<i>mmol_c g⁻¹</i>	<i>wt%</i>	<i>wt%</i>	<i>Å</i>	<i>Å</i>
Mg ₂ Al	2.00	1.97	0.337	4.73	19.1	10.8	7.68	2.91
Mg ₃ Al	3.00	2.96	0.253	3.72	22.2	8.3	7.94	3.17
Mg ₄ Al	4.00	3.74	0.211	3.20	23.4	6.9	7.97	3.20

233

234
 235 Figure 1: The (003) XRD reflection (a) and the FTIR spectra (b) of the Mg₂Al, Mg₃Al and Mg₄Al LDHs, either in as-synthesized
 236 form (AS) or after reaction with orthophosphate (PO₄) or trimetaphosphate (P₃O₉).

237
 238 **3.2. Uptake of PO₄ and P₃O₉ by as-synthesized LDHs**
 239 The PO₄ and P₃O₉ uptake by the three as-synthesized LDHs was assessed by determining the PO₄ and P₃O₉
 240 adsorption isotherms (Figure 2a). For all LDHs, the maximum P uptake that could be obtained was higher
 241 when loaded with P₃O₉ compared to with PO₄, *i.e.* 1.25 fold higher for Mg₂Al, 1.52 fold higher for Mg₃Al
 242 and 1.60 fold higher for Mg₄Al. These P uptake results can be influenced by *i)* the access of PO₄ and P₃O₉
 243 to bonding sites in the interlayer gallery (*i.e.* intercalation) and *ii)* the charge speciation of these two P

244 compounds. Using the FTIR spectra and XRD patterns of the obtained materials, the uptake mechanisms
245 of PO₄ and P₃O₉ were revealed.

246 For the Mg₂Al LDH, the maximum PO₄ uptake was 54 mg P g⁻¹, which was in line with earlier studies [9,32].
247 Using FTIR, the chemical speciation of PO₄ in Mg₂Al could be derived (Figure 1b). The band at 1081 cm⁻¹
248 could be attributed to HPO₄²⁻, while the band at 1008 cm⁻¹ also suggested the presence of PO₄³⁻ [33]. With
249 the assumption of an equimolar HPO₄²⁻/PO₄³⁻ ratio of adsorbed PO₄ (*i.e.* 1 mole of P compensates 2.5
250 moles of positive layer charge) and the theoretical AEC of the Mg₂Al LDH (Table 1), the fraction of the AEC
251 of the LDHs occupied by PO₄ was calculated (Figure 2b). This approach suggested that, at maximum
252 capacity, >90% of the AEC was occupied by PO₄. The XRD pattern of the obtained PO₄-exchanged material
253 showed an interlayer spacing of ~3.66 Å, indicating a clear PO₄ intercalation according to earlier work [17].
254 The near-absence of the (003) reflection, attributed to the initial interlayer anion population (Cl⁻, CO₃²⁻,
255 OH⁻), confirmed the high PO₄ loading rate with respect to the AEC of the Mg₂Al LDH. For the Mg₃Al LDH,
256 the maximum PO₄ uptake was 48 mg P g⁻¹. The FTIR spectrum indicated bands at 1081 cm⁻¹ and 1120 cm⁻¹
257 ¹, which were attributed to HPO₄²⁻ [33]. The higher charge of PO₄ in the Mg₂Al LDH (*i.e.* HPO₄²⁻/PO₄³⁻)
258 compared to in the Mg₃Al LDH (*i.e.* HPO₄²⁻) was likely the result of *i)* the higher intrinsic alkalinity of the
259 Mg₂Al LDH, attributed to exchangeable OH⁻ and CO₃²⁻ anions in that LDH, also causing more alkaline
260 exchange solutions (Figure S2, LDH incubations without P addition), and *ii)* the higher charge density of
261 the metal hydroxide layers of the Mg₂Al LDH in comparison with those of the Mg₃Al LDH, which favored
262 the uptake of PO₄ anions with higher charge. With the assumption of PO₄ adsorption by the Mg₃Al LDH in
263 the form of HPO₄²⁻ (*i.e.* 1 mole of P compensates 2 moles of positive layer charge), it was calculated that
264 83% of the AEC of the Mg₃Al LDH was occupied by PO₄ (Figure 2b). Despite this relatively high PO₄ uptake,
265 a PO₄-loaded LDH with relatively small interlayer spacing of 3.13 Å was obtained, an aspect of Mg₃Al LDHs
266 also observed in earlier studies [9,34,35]. For the Mg₄Al LDH, the maximum PO₄ uptake was only 26 mg P
267 g⁻¹. The FTIR spectrum indicated a band at 1085 cm⁻¹, which could be attributed to HPO₄²⁻ [33]. With this

268 PO₄ speciation, it was calculated that PO₄ only occupied up to 52% of the AEC of the Mg₄Al LDH (Figure
269 2b). Together with the small interlayer spacing of 3.19 Å (Figure 1a), this suggested that only very little
270 PO₄ was intercalated in the Mg₄Al LDH.

271 The highest P uptake of the LDHs was obtained by loading Mg₃Al with P₃O₉, *i.e.* 73 mg P g⁻¹ (Fig. 2a). The
272 FTIR spectrum of the obtained P₃O₉-exchanged Mg₃Al LDH showed a clear fingerprint of P₃O₉, with bands
273 at 999 cm⁻¹, 1117 cm⁻¹, 1130 cm⁻¹, 1245 cm⁻¹ and 1263 cm⁻¹ [36,37], while bands associated to PO₄
274 remained absent. This confirmed the stability of P₃O₉ in these reaction conditions and, therefore, it could
275 be assumed that P₃O₉ was indeed adsorbed as P₃O₉³⁻ (*i.e.* 1 mole of P compensates 1 mole of positive layer
276 charge). The charge calculations indicated that up to 63% of the AEC of Mg₃Al LDH could be occupied by
277 P₃O₉ (Figure 2b). This was illustrated by the strong (003) XRD reflection associated with a 4.48 Å interlayer
278 spacing, caused by intercalated P₃O₉ anions with a tilted orientation with respect to the basal plane (Figure
279 S3). A (003) XRD reflection attributed to the initial interlayer Cl⁻ anion population remained present for
280 the P₃O₉-exchanged Mg₃Al LDH, demonstrating that the interlayer anion population was not fully
281 exchanged with P₃O₉. With Mg₄Al, a maximum P₃O₉ uptake of 42 mg P g⁻¹ was obtained, and also here the
282 FTIR spectrum showed clear bands of P₃O₉, while bands of PO₄ remained absent [36]. It was calculated
283 that, at maximum capacity, P₃O₉ occupied only 42% of the AEC of the Mg₄Al LDH (Figure 2b). The slightly
284 asymmetric (003) reflection obtained for the P₃O₉-exchanged Mg₄Al LDH suggests some P₃O₉ intercalation
285 could have taken place, yet this remained limited (Figure 1a).

286 With the incubation of Mg₂Al in P₃O₉ solutions, a maximum uptake of only 67 mg P g⁻¹ was recorded (Figure
287 2a), *i.e.* below that of the Mg₃Al. Here, with the characterization of the obtained material, a more careful
288 interpretation was required. In the FTIR spectrum of the Mg₂Al LDH after treatment in the P₃O₉ solution,
289 two characteristic bands for P₃O₉ at ~1000 cm⁻¹ and ~1260 cm⁻¹ were absent. Hence, with the remaining
290 bands at 1132 cm⁻¹ and 1233cm⁻¹, it appeared that P₃O₁₀ (linear triphosphate), and thus not the cyclic

291 P_3O_9 , was the main species exchanged on the LDH (Eq. 1, also allowing further hydrolysis via Eq. 2 and 3)
292 [38,39].

296 The XRD pattern showed a (003) reflection associated with a 4.06 Å interlayer spacing, which could relate
297 to P_3O_{10} anions oriented parallel with the basal plane. Generally, enhanced polyphosphate hydrolysis in
298 abiotic systems is caused by more acid conditions, higher temperature, higher solution ionic strength or
299 higher concentration of complexing cations [40,41]. Here, the enhanced hydrolysis of P_3O_9 in the presence
300 of Mg_2Al was likely the result of the latter, *i.e.* the more pronounced presence of Al^{3+} in the suspension of
301 Mg_2Al and the higher Al content of the Mg_2Al solid phase in comparison with those of Mg_3Al and Mg_4Al .
302 Earlier studies also showed that Al^{3+} in solution can catalyze the degradation of P_3O_9 to linear polymeric P
303 compounds, while solid Al-oxyhydroxides negatively affect the stability of short-chain polymeric P [41,42].
304 Temperature was considered not to be a factor since the incubation temperature was the same for all
305 LDH suspensions, and also pH was likely not a determining factor since the solution pH of the Mg_2Al
306 suspensions was even slightly higher than that of the other LDHs (Figure S2, at maximum P loading). The
307 charge calculations indicated that, if indeed P was only taken up as P_3O_{10} by Mg_2Al (*i.e.* 1 mole of P
308 compensates 1.3 mole of positive layer charge, assuming a $HP_3O_{10}^{4-}$ species for the given conditions), up
309 to 61% of the AEC of Mg_2Al LDH was occupied by P_3O_{10} (Figure 2b) [43]. A partial intercalation of P_3O_{10} in
310 Mg_2Al was also consistent with the XRD pattern of the material after incubation in a P_3O_9 solution (Figure
311 1a).

312

313

314 Figure 2: Adsorption isotherms of the Mg_2Al , Mg_3Al and Mg_4Al LDHs for orthophosphate (PO_4) and trimetaphosphate (P_3O_9), with
 315 the P uptake presented as the measured P uptake in $mg\ P\ g^{-1}$ (a) and as the calculated relative occupation of AEC of the specific
 316 LDH by the adsorbed P compound based on its inferred speciation (b).

317

318 3.3. Uptake of PO_4 and P_3O_9 by calcined LDHs

319 A common approach to increase the PO_4 adsorption by LDHs is the calcination of the as-synthesized LDHs

320 prior to adsorption [44]. The calcination of LDHs at temperatures above 300 °C results in the formation of

321 mixed oxide phases, and thus the loss of the interlayer anions (if these are converted to volatile

322 compounds). Upon rehydration, the metastable mixed oxides can regain the LDH structure and adsorb

323 anions from that rehydration solution. This approach is especially beneficial when an LDH is used that

324 contains an intercalated anion that cannot be replaced by target anions in solutions (*e.g.* CO_3^{2-} exchanged

325 LDHs), but also the increase of the specific surface area as a result of calcination has a proven positive

326 effect on anion uptake [45]. Since in exchange experiments with as-synthesized Mg₂Al and Mg₃Al LDHs no
327 full P₃O₉-exchanged LDHs were obtained, Mg₂Al and Mg₃Al LDHs calcined at varying temperatures were
328 tested for P₃O₉ uptake. The effect of calcination temperature on the stability of the LDHs was investigated
329 with TGA (Figure 3). Up to a temperature of 220 °C for the Mg₂Al LDH and 200 °C for the Mg₃Al LDH, the
330 weight loss was attributed to the elimination of water (poorly-bound water below 100 °C, interlayer water
331 above 100 °C) [46], which accounted for ~12 wt% with Mg₂Al and ~14 wt% with Mg₃Al. As an example,
332 the water elimination reaction of the Mg₃Al LDH was the following:

334 From 200 °C onwards, strong weight drops were recorded, which continued to 550 °C. These weight losses
335 were the result of the dehydroxylation, dechlorination and, possibly, decarbonation of the LDHs,
336 indicating the conversion to mixed oxide phases, *i.e.* mixed MgO-Al₂O₃ phases [46]. For the Mg₃Al LDH,
337 the following reaction was expected:

339 The weight losses obtained for the LDHs during calcination treatments showed very similar trends as the
340 TGA plots. However, the recorded weight losses during the calcination treatments were slightly above
341 those of the TGA measurements (Figure 3, Table S1), which likely was due to longer residence times in the
342 calcination furnace [47].

343

344 Figure 3: TGA plots of the Mg₂Al and Mg₃Al LDHs, presented with the recorded weight loss (calc) from the LDHs during the
 345 calcination treatments.

346

347 The PO₄ and P₃O₉ uptake by calcined Mg₂Al and Mg₃Al LDHs was assessed in solutions of equal P content,
 348 and compared with that of the as-synthesized LDHs. The obtained P uptake values for both P compounds
 349 were recalculated to P uptake per g of LDH material prior to calcination (*i.e.* as-synthesized form), thereby
 350 compensating for the weight loss during calcination to allow the comparison of the actual adsorption
 351 efficiency of the obtained materials (Figure 4). The adsorption results showed a slight beneficial effect of
 352 calcination at 300 °C for PO₄ adsorption by both LDHs, which could be attributed to reduced competition
 353 with other anions (Cl⁻, CO₃²⁻, OH⁻). With increasing calcination temperatures from 300 °C onwards, the PO₄
 354 adsorption again decreased to values around 25 mg P g⁻¹. For P₃O₉ uptake, however, LDH calcination
 355 proved to be detrimental, especially for the Mg₃Al LDH which displayed a strong drop in P₃O₉ adsorption
 356 as a result of calcination at relatively low temperatures. The (003) reflections in the XRD patterns of the
 357 obtained P₃O₉-loaded materials indicated that P₃O₉ intercalation became less pronounced with increasing
 358 calcination temperatures (Figure 4), although the loss of interlayer anions from the as-synthesized LDHs
 359 should in theory facilitate P₃O₉ intercalation. That might be explained by the higher pH of the exchange
 360 solutions with calcined materials compared to not calcined ones and a higher pH observed for the solution

361 with P_3O_9 than with PO_4 (Figure S4). The calcination of LDH and the corresponding phase transition to
362 mixed oxides resulted in the production of excess acidity, which likely was lost to the atmosphere (Eq. 5,
363 but also loss of possible carbonates as CO_2). The rehydration treatment of the calcined materials,
364 therefore, resulted in a consumption of protons from the exchange solutions to re-establish the LDH
365 phase. Indeed, higher calcination temperatures for both the Mg_2Al and Mg_3Al LDHs caused increasingly
366 higher pH values for the P_3O_9 solutions. A similar trend was obtained for the PO_4 solutions, yet the stronger
367 pH buffering of the PO_4 solutions resulted in lower pH values than for the P_3O_9 solutions. Previous studies
368 have shown negative effects of alkaline conditions on PO_4 adsorption by LDHs [32,44,48], which could be
369 linked to *i)* the deprotonation of PO_4 anions in the system (higher fraction as PO_4^{3-}), which reduces the
370 absolute amount of P that can be adsorbed via charge interactions, *ii)* the deprotonation of pH-dependent
371 surface sites, causing a decrease of the effective AEC and *iii)* enhanced competition for anion exchange
372 sorption by OH^- anions. No such studies have been carried out for P_3O_9 , but similar effects likely apply.
373 Especially the latter effect of competition with OH^- anions could also have strongly reduced the P_3O_9
374 adsorption by the calcined LDHs because of their high selectivity for OH^- anions, which have a relatively
375 high charge density in comparison with P_3O_9 anions. Naturally, hydrolysis of P_3O_9 could also have taken
376 place in these exchange solutions. If hydrolysis of P_3O_9 (to P_3O_{10} , or even to PO_4) was again more
377 pronounced for the Mg_2Al -based materials than the Mg_3Al -based materials, this could explain why some
378 P intercalation remained present with Mg_2Al -based calcined materials (*i.e.* as PO_4) and P intercalation
379 remained absent for all Mg_3Al -based calcined materials. Overall, it could be concluded that LDH
380 calcination is not a suitable approach to facilitate P_3O_9 intercalation and increase P_3O_9 uptake by LDHs.

381
 382 Figure 4: The PO₄ and P₃O₉ uptake (P uptake per g of LDH material prior to calcination) by the Mg₂Al and Mg₃Al LDHs and their
 383 calcination products, presented with the (003) XRD reflection of the materials treated with P₃O₉.

384
 385 **3.4. Release of PO₄ and P₃O₉ from LDHs**

386 The P release from the Mg₂Al and Mg₃Al LDHs (non-calcined), loaded with either PO₄ or P₃O₉, was
 387 investigated in a 2-mM NaHCO₃ solution to simulate anion exchange with CO₃ in a soil environment and
 388 that release was compared with that from soluble NaH₂PO₄ and Na₃P₃O₉ salts. As expected, P from the
 389 soluble salts passed quickly through the dialysis membrane (>90% in 48 h, Figure S5). After 168 h, the
 390 Mg₂Al LDH had released 42% of P and the Mg₃Al LDH 52% of P when loaded with PO₄ (Figure 5), which
 391 was comparable to values from earlier studies [9,49]. During the same period, the P release from the LDHs
 392 loaded with P₃O₉ was significantly lower, with 25% of P released from the Mg₂Al LDH and 30% of P from
 393 the Mg₃Al LDH. This was likely linked to more pronounced diffusion limitations in the interlayer during the
 394 anion exchange of polymeric phosphate with CO₃, in comparison with the smaller PO₄ anions. At the end
 395 of the dialysis, the pH of the outer solution did not differ largely between the different treatments, which
 396 was the result of the low fertilizer doses (high L:S ratio) in a NaHCO₃ solution with strong pH buffering
 397 capacity (Table S2).

398
 399 Figure 5: The P release from Mg₂Al and Mg₃Al LDHs, loaded with either PO₄ or P₃O₉, in a 2 mM NaHCO₃ solution and measured
 400 either as total P (TP, ICP-OES analysis) or as molybdate-reactive P (MRP, colorimetric analysis), presented as a function of the
 401 dialysis time. Error bars represent the standard error (n=2).

402

403 Next to measurements of total P (TP) release, also the molybdate reactive P (MRP) release was
 404 determined with the aim of distinguishing the speciation of the desorbed P, *i.e.* the stability of the P₃O₉
 405 during adsorption and subsequent desorption by the LDHs. As expected, the TP and MRP quantification
 406 of the release from the PO₄-loaded LDHs was the same for both measurement techniques. Dialysis results
 407 for the Na₃P₃O₉ salt solution showed that MRP was <1% of the TP after 168 h (Figure S5). For the P₃O₉-
 408 loaded Mg₃Al LDH, MRP amounted to 12% of the TP after 168 h dialysis (Figure 5). Thus, these results
 409 suggested that a small amount of P₃O₉ from the Mg₃Al LDH was converted to PO₄, but that there was
 410 relatively good stability of P₃O₉ *i)* during the loading on Mg₃Al, which was thus in agreement with the
 411 characterization results of the P₃O₉-loading of the Mg₃Al LDH (Figure 1), *ii)* during desorption in the CO₃
 412 exchange solution and *iii)* after desorption in the CO₃ exchange solution. In contrast, no difference
 413 between the TP and MRP measurements of the desorbed P was recorded for the P₃O₉-loaded Mg₂Al LDH
 414 (Figure 5). This suggests that the hydrolysis of P₃O₉ in the presence of Mg₂Al, as evidenced by the material
 415 characterization of the loading step (Figure 1), further continued during the dialysis in the CO₃ exchange
 416 solution (Eq. 2 and 3). Hence, no polymeric P was present in the Mg₂Al exchange solution.

417

418 **3.5. Soil incubation of PO₄ and P₃O₉ loaded LDH**

419 The P solubility with PO₄-Mg₃Al LDH and P₃O₉-Mg₃Al LDH application in a calcareous soil was assessed,
420 and compared to that of soluble PO₄ and P₃O₉ salts (Figure 6). The observed trends in P solubility (as
421 assessed with CaCl₂ extractions) with application of soluble PO₄ and P₃O₉ fertilizers were in line with earlier
422 work [24]. Highest P solubility was obtained for NaH₂PO₄ and KH₂PO₄ at the start of the incubation, with
423 the P solubility for NaH₂PO₄ exceeding that for KH₂PO₄ at most measurements, likely due to the enhanced
424 soil dispersion in the NaH₂PO₄ treatment resulting in a more pronounced contribution of colloidal-bound
425 P. The P solubility for these soluble PO₄ treatments dropped significantly over the course of 49 days,
426 indicating P fixation in soil. The soluble P₃O₉ treatment did not show these high values of P solubility, and
427 the decrease in P solubility over time was less pronounced.

428 The PO₄-Mg₃Al and P₃O₉-Mg₃Al LDH fertilizers showed slightly lower TP and MRP extraction values in
429 comparison with their respective soluble P salts. The PO₄-Mg₃Al LDH was able to maintain a very constant
430 P solubility over the course of the incubation, as likely the exchange properties of the LDH were able to
431 control the release of PO₄ in response to the soil solution P concentration. With the P₃O₉-Mg₃Al LDH, the
432 P solubility was significantly lower than that with the PO₄-Mg₃Al up to 21 d, while at long incubation times
433 (after 21 d) also a constant P solubility was obtained converging towards the solubility with the PO₄-Mg₃Al
434 LDH. At these short incubation times, the Na₃P₃O₉ and the P₃O₉-Mg₃Al LDH treatments both showed lower
435 solubility of P in comparison with their respective PO₄ treatment, the NaH₂PO₄ and PO₄-Mg₃Al LDH
436 treatments. Interestingly, this trend was present for both the TP and MRP measurements of the CaCl₂
437 extract (Figure 6), which suggested that polymeric P was not a significant fraction of the extracted P. For
438 the interpretation of this effect, it should be noted that P₃O₉ hydrolysis in soils takes place at a much
439 higher rate in comparison with solution conditions due to enzymatic activity [21]. Also, adsorption of P₃O₉
440 in soil is typically less strong than that of PO₄, while sorption of short-chain polymeric P compounds P₂O₇

441 (pyrophosphate) and P_3O_{10} (tripolyphosphate) is stronger than that of PO_4 [50]. Therefore, the clear
442 increase in TP/MRP extraction of the $Na_3P_3O_9$ and P_3O_9 - Mg_3Al LDH treatments up to day 21 was attributed
443 to *i)* the fast hydrolysis of released P_3O_9 to polymeric hydrolysis products P_2O_7 and P_3O_{10} (Eq. 1 and 2), *ii)*
444 the subsequent sorption of P_2O_7 and P_3O_{10} on soil surfaces and *iii)* a slower hydrolysis of adsorbed
445 polymeric P to PO_4 (Eq. 3), of which the latter then contributed to the measured extractable P fraction.
446 Also, the significantly slower P release from the P_3O_9 - Mg_3Al LDH in comparison with the PO_4 - Mg_3Al LDH,
447 as observed in the release experiment (Figure 5), could be an additional explanation for the P extraction
448 results in the LDH treatment at short incubation times. At long incubation times, the differences in P
449 extractability among the soluble fertilizers (KH_2PO_4 vs $Na_3P_3O_9$) and among the LDH fertilizers (PO_4 vs P_3O_9
450 loaded) became negligible. The pH of the $CaCl_2$ extraction solutions was also measured, but did not differ
451 largely between the different treatments (Figure S6).

452 In this incubation study, the application of powdered slow-release P fertilizers did not result in an
453 improved P solubility compared to that of powdered soluble P fertilizers. However, it has been shown that
454 P availability from soluble P to a calcareous soil is particularly challenging when P is applied in granular
455 form, as high local P concentrations in the fertosphere of soluble fertilizers can trigger P fixation by Ca-P
456 precipitation [3]. Further research could therefore explore the potential of slow-release PO_4 and P_3O_9 LDH
457 fertilizers in granular form to enhance long-term P availability in calcareous soils in comparison with
458 conventional granular P fertilizers.

459

460
 461 Figure 6: Concentration of soluble P extracted from soil using 1 mM CaCl₂, measured either as TP (ICP-OES analysis) (a) or as MRP
 462 (colorimetric analysis) (b), as a function of the incubation time. The soils were incubated with an equal total P dose as soluble P
 463 compounds (NaH₂PO₄, Na₃P₃O₉, KH₂PO₄), LDH-P compounds (PO₄-Mg₃Al LDH, P₃O₉-Mg₃Al LDH), or without added P (control).
 464 Error bars represent the standard error (n=3).

465
 466 **Conclusions**

467 This study investigated the development of polyphosphate-loaded LDHs as an alternative LDH-based P
 468 fertilizer with increased P content. For the three as-synthesized LDHs, loading with P₃O₉ increased the P
 469 uptake compared to loading with PO₄, while it was most promising for the Mg₃Al LDH which adsorbed
 470 50% more P as P₃O₉. However, none of the treatments were successful in obtaining the theoretical
 471 maximum based on the AEC, i.e. up to 12 wt% P was not achieved. This is due to *i*) incomplete loading of
 472 the LDH interlayer gallery with P₃O₉ as a result of the limited affinity of the LDHs for the P₃O₉ anion (low
 473 anion charge density), or *ii*) the conversion of P₃O₉ to linear/shorter polymers (with Mg₂Al LDH), which
 474 have a higher molar charge/P ratio. Also with the use of calcined MgAl LDHs, it was not possible to further
 475 increase P₃O₉ uptake. Dialysis experiments showed that the P₃O₉-loaded Mg₃Al merely released polymeric
 476 P, whereas the P₃O₉-loaded Mg₂Al released depolymerized PO₄ as a result of enhanced hydrolysis in the
 477 presence of an Al-rich phase. Furthermore, the P release from P₃O₉-loaded LDHs was slower in comparison
 478 with that of PO₄-loaded LDHs. Finally, with the application of powdered LDH fertilizers to a calcareous soil,

479 at short incubation times (up to 21 d) the P extractable by CaCl_2 from soil was significantly lower compared
480 to that of water-soluble P_3O_9 and PO_4 fertilizers, likely as a result of fast P_3O_9 hydrolysis and strong sorption
481 of linear polymeric P in the soil. At longer incubation times, the solubility of P in soil after addition of the
482 P_3O_9 -loaded LDH fertilizer converged to that of the PO_4 -loaded LDH fertilizer, but did not exceed that of
483 the water-soluble P_3O_9 and PO_4 fertilizers.

484

485 **Acknowledgements**

486 The authors would like to thank Hao Yang for technical assistance and Lei Xia, Dries Grauwels and Florian
487 Lauryssen for ICP-OES measurements. Finally, the corresponding author is grateful for a MSCA-IF-GF
488 fellowship. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and
489 innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 890943. This publication
490 reflects only the authors' view, exempting the Commission from any liability.

491 **References**

- 492 [1] J. Helin, H.P. Weikard, A model for estimating phosphorus requirements of world food production, *Agric. Syst.* 176
493 (2019) 102666. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2019.102666>.
- 494 [2] G. Meyer, M.J. Bell, E. Lombi, C.L. Doolette, G. Brunetti, E.H. Novotny, W. Klysubun, Y. Zhang, P.M. Kopittke,
495 Phosphorus speciation in the fertosphere of highly concentrated fertilizer bands, *Geoderma*. 403 (2021) 115208.
496 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2021.115208>.
- 497 [3] E. Lombi, M.J. McLaughlin, C. Johnston, R.D. Armstrong, R.E. Holloway, Mobility and Lability of Phosphorus from
498 Granular and Fluid Monoammonium Phosphate Differs in a Calcareous Soil, *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.* 68 (2004) 682–689.
499 <https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj2004.6820>.
- 500 [4] F. Degryse, R. Baird, R.C. Silva, M.J. McLaughlin, Dissolution rate and agronomic effectiveness of struvite fertilizers –
501 effect of soil pH , granulation and base excess, *Plant Soil.* (2017) 139–152. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-016-2990-2>.
- 502 [5] I.B. Andelkovic, S. Kabiri, E. Tavakkoli, J.K. Kirby, M.J. McLaughlin, D. Losic, Graphene oxide-Fe(III) composite containing
503 phosphate – A novel slow release fertilizer for improved agriculture management, *J. Clean. Prod.* 185 (2018) 97–104.
504 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.03.050>.
- 505 [6] A.K. Bansiwala, S.S. Rayalu, N.K. Labhsetwar, A.A. Juwarkar, S. Devotta, Surfactant-modified zeolite as a slow release
506 fertilizer for phosphorus, *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 54 (2006) 4773–4779. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf060034b>.
- 507 [7] M. Anstoetz, T.J. Rose, M.W. Clark, L.H. Yee, C.A. Raymond, T. Vancov, Novel applications for oxalate-phosphate-amine
508 metal-organic-frameworks (OPA-MOFs): Can an iron-based OPA-MOF be used as slow-release fertilizer?, *PLoS One.* 10
509 (2015) 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0144169>.
- 510 [8] Y. Yao, B. Gao, J. Chen, L. Yang, Engineered biochar reclaiming phosphate from aqueous solutions: Mechanisms and
511 potential application as a slow-release fertilizer, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 47 (2013) 8700–8708.
512 <https://doi.org/10.1021/es4012977>.
- 513 [9] M. Everaert, R. Warrinnier, S. Baken, J.-P. Gustafsson, D. De Vos, E. Smolders, Phosphate-Exchanged Mg-Al Layered
514 Double Hydroxides: A New Slow Release Phosphate Fertilizer, *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.* 4 (2016).
515 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssuschemeng.6b00778>.
- 516 [10] M.P. Bernardo, G.G.F. Guimarães, V.F. Majaron, C. Ribeiro, Controlled Release of Phosphate from Layered Double

- 517 Hydroxide Structures: Dynamics in Soil and Application as Smart Fertilizer, *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.* 6 (2018) 5152–
518 5161. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssuschemeng.7b04806>.
- 519 [11] L.P.F. Benício, V.R.L. Constantino, F.G. Pinto, L. Vergütz, J. Tronto, L.M. Da Costa, Layered Double Hydroxides: New
520 Technology in Phosphate Fertilizers Based on Nanostructured Materials, *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.* 5 (2017) 399–409.
521 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssuschemeng.6b01784>.
- 522 [12] M. Everaert, F. Degryse, M. McLaughlin, D. De Vos, E. Smolders, Agronomic Effectiveness of Granulated and Powdered
523 P-Exchanged Mg–Al LDH Relative to Struvite and MAP, *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 65 (n.d.) 6736–6744.
524 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jafc.7b01031>.
- 525 [13] M. Everaert, R.C. da Silva, F. Degryse, M.J. McLaughlin, E. Smolders, Limited dissolved phosphorus runoff losses from
526 layered double hydroxide and struvite fertilizers in a rainfall simulation study, *J. Environ. Qual.* 47 (2018).
527 <https://doi.org/10.2134/jeq2017.07.0282>.
- 528 [14] X. Jiang, B. Yan, J. Chen, W. Li, J. Hu, Y. Guan, Transport and retention of phosphorus in soil with addition of Mg–Al
529 layered double hydroxides: Effects of material dosage, flow velocity and pH, *Chem. Eng. J.* 378 (2019) 122154.
530 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2019.122154>.
- 531 [15] M. Everaert, F. Degryse, M.J. McLaughlin, D. De Vos, E. Smolders, Agronomic Effectiveness of Granulated and
532 Powdered P-Exchanged Mg–Al LDH Relative to Struvite and MAP, *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 65 (2017) 6736–6744.
533 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jafc.7b01031>.
- 534 [16] A.E. Johnston, I.R. Richards, Effectiveness of Different Precipitated Phosphates Phosphorus Sources for Plants,
535 *Phosphorus Res. Bull.* 15 (2004) 52–59.
- 536 [17] M. Everaert, K. Dox, J.A. Steele, D. De Vos, E. Smolders, Solid-state speciation of interlayer anions in layered double
537 hydroxides, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 537 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcis.2018.11.010>.
- 538 [18] R. Benhiti, A.A. Ichou, A. Zaghoul, R. Aziam, G. Carja, M. Zerbet, Synthesis , characterization , and comparative study of
539 MgAl-LDHs prepared by standard coprecipitation and urea hydrolysis methods for phosphate removal, *Environ. Sci.*
540 *Pollut. Res.* 27 (2020) 45767–45774.
- 541 [19] M.L. Parello, R. Rojas, C.E. Giacomelli, Dissolution kinetics and mechanism of Mg–Al layered double hydroxides: A
542 simple approach to describe drug release in acid media, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 351 (2010) 134–139.

- 543 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcis.2010.07.053>.
- 544 [20] C. V. Luengo, M.A. Volpe, M.J. Avena, High sorption of phosphate on Mg-Al layered double hydroxides: Kinetics and
545 equilibrium, *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 5 (2017) 4656–4662. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2017.08.051>.
- 546 [21] L.O. Torres-Dorante, N. Claassen, B. Steingrobe, H.W. Olf, Fertilizer-use efficiency of different inorganic polyphosphate
547 sources: Effects on soil P availability and plant P acquisition during early growth of corn, *J. Plant Nutr. Soil Sci.* 169
548 (2006) 509–515. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jpln.200520584>.
- 549 [22] B.U. Grzmil, B. Kic, Pyro- and tripolyphosphates and citrates as the complexing agents for micronutrients in liquid
550 fertilizers, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 41 (2002) 139–144. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ie010223d>.
- 551 [23] J. Zhou, Z. Ping, S. Qiao, Q. Liu, Y. Xu, G. Qian, Enhanced removal of triphosphate by MgCaFe-Cl-LDH : Synergism of
552 precipitation with intercalation and surface uptake, *J. Hazard. Mater.* 189 (2011) 586–594.
553 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2011.02.078>.
- 554 [24] L.O. Torres-Dorante, N. Claassen, B. Steingrobe, H.W. Olf, Hydrolysis rates of inorganic polyphosphates in aqueous
555 solution as well as in soils and effects on P availability, *J. Plant Nutr. Soil Sci.* 168 (2005) 352–358.
556 <https://doi.org/10.1002/jpln.200420494>.
- 557 [25] K. Dox, M. Everaert, R. Merckx, E. Smolders, Optimization of phosphate recovery from urine by layered double
558 hydroxides, *Sci. Total Environ.* 682 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.05.181>.
- 559 [26] C. Van Moorleghe, L. Six, F. Degryse, E. Smolders, R. Merckx, Effect of Organic P Forms and P Present in Inorganic
560 Colloids on the Determination of Dissolved P in Environmental Samples by the Diffusive Gradient in Thin Films
561 Technique, Ion Chromatography, and Colorimetry, *Anal. Chem.* 83 (2011) 5317–5323.
- 562 [27] U. Schwertmann, Differenzierung der Eisenoxide des Bodens durch Extraktion mit Ammoniumoxalat-Lösung,
563 *Pflanzenernaehr., Dueng., Bodenkd.* 105 (1964) 194–202.
- 564 [28] S. Miyata, The Syntheses of Hydrotalcite-Like Compounds and Their Structures and Physico-Chemical Properties—I: the
565 Systems $Mg_{2+}-Al_{3+}-NO_{3-}$, $Mg_{2+}-Al_{3+}-Cl-$, $Mg_{2+}-Al_{3+}-ClO_{4-}$, $Ni_{2+}-Al_{3+}-Cl-$ and $Zn_{2+}-Al_{3+}-Cl-$, *Clays Clay Miner.* 23
566 (1975) 369–375. <https://doi.org/10.1346/CCMN.1975.0230508>.
- 567 [29] J. Matusik, Y. Deng, Fumonisin B1 Interaction with Mg-Al and Mg-Fe Layered Double Hydroxides: Removal Efficiency
568 and Mechanisms, (2020) 1–17.

- 569 [30] R. Sasai, H. Sato, M. Sugata, T. Fujimura, S. Ishihara, K. Deguchi, S. Ohki, M. Tansho, T. Shimizu, N. Oita, M. Numoto, Y.
570 Fujii, S. Kawaguchi, Y. Matsuoka, K. Hagura, T. Abe, C. Moriyoshi, Why Do Carbonate Anions Have Extremely High
571 Stability in the Interlayer Space of Layered Double Hydroxides? Case Study of Layered Double Hydroxide Consisting of
572 Mg and Al (Mg/Al = 2), *Inorg. Chem.* 58 (2019) 10928–10935. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.inorgchem.9b01365>.
- 573 [31] J.T. Kloprogge, R.L. Frost, Fourier transform infrared and Raman spectroscopic study of the local structure of Mg-, Ni-,
574 and Co-hydrotalcites, *J. Solid State Chem.* 146 (1999) 506–515. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jssc.1999.8413>.
- 575 [32] C. Novillo, D. Guaya, A. Allen-Perkins Avendaño, C. Armijos, J.L. Cortina, I. Cota, Evaluation of phosphate removal
576 capacity of Mg/Al layered double hydroxides from aqueous solutions, *Fuel.* 138 (2014) 72–79.
577 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2014.07.010>.
- 578 [33] E.J. Elzinga, D.L. Sparks, Phosphate adsorption onto hematite: An in situ ATR-FTIR investigation of the effects of pH and
579 loading level on the mode of phosphate surface complexation, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 308 (2007) 53–70.
580 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcis.2006.12.061>.
- 581 [34] L.P.F. Benício, D. Eulálio, L. de Moura Guimarães, F.G. Pinto, L.M. Da Costa, J. Tronto, Layered double hydroxides as
582 hosting matrices for storage and slow release of phosphate analyzed by stirred-flow method, *Mater. Res.* 21 (2018).
583 <https://doi.org/10.1590/1980-5373-mr-2017-1004>.
- 584 [35] S. Bougacha Ghorbel, F. Medina, A. Ghorbel, A.M. Segarra, Phosphoric acid intercalated Mg-Al hydrotalcite-like
585 compounds for catalytic carboxylation reaction of methanol in a continuous system, *Appl. Catal. A Gen.* 493 (2015)
586 142–148. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apcata.2015.01.004>.
- 587 [36] K. Nahdi, M. Férid, M.T. Ayadi, Chemical preparation and thermal behavior of neodymium cyclotriphosphate
588 pentahydrate NdP₃O₉·5H₂O: A study by Controlled Rate Thermal Analysis (CRTA), *Thermochim. Acta.* 487 (2009) 54–
589 59. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tca.2009.01.014>.
- 590 [37] O.A. Cavalcanti, C.C. Da Silva, E.A.G. Pineda, A.A.W. Hechenleitner, Synthesis and characterization of phosphated
591 crosslinked chondroitin sulfate: Potential ingredient for specific drug delivery, *Acta Farm. Bonaer.* 24 (2005) 234–238.
- 592 [38] L.M. Busman, M.A. Tabatabai, Hydrolysis of Trimetaphosphate in Soils, *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.* 49 (1985) 630–636.
593 <https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj1985.03615995004900030021x>.
- 594 [39] A.F. Tomaz, S.M.S. de Carvalho, R.C. Barbosa, S.M.L. Silva, M.A.S. Gutierrez, A.G.B. de Lima, M.V.L. Fook, Ionically

- 595 crosslinked chitosan membranes used as drug carriers for cancer therapy application, *Materials (Basel)*. 11 (2018) 1–
596 18. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma11102051>.
- 597 [40] T.M. McBeath, E. Lombi, M.J. McLaughlin, E.K. Bünemann, Polyphosphate-fertilizer solution stability with time,
598 temperature, and pH, *J. Plant Nutr. Soil Sci.* 170 (2007) 387–391. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jpln.200625166>.
- 599 [41] A.W. Frazier, E.F. Dillard, Ionic Effects on the Hydrolysis of Polyphosphates in Liquid Fertilizers, *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 29
600 (1981) 695–698. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf00106a002>.
- 601 [42] G. Kura, Y. Miyazaki, J. Sakamoto, Additional reactions of inorganic condensed phosphate oligomers during their
602 degradation reactions in the presence of aluminum(III) ions, *Polyhedron*. 17 (1998) 1907–1912.
603 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-5387\(97\)00514-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-5387(97)00514-7).
- 604 [43] M. Gierszewska, J. Ostrowska-czubenko, Chitosan-based membranes with different ionic crosslinking density for
605 pharmaceutical and industrial applications, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 153 (2016) 501–511.
606 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2016.07.126>.
- 607 [44] J. Das, B.S. Patra, N. Baliarsingh, K.M. Parida, Adsorption of phosphate by layered double hydroxides in aqueous
608 solutions, *Appl. Clay Sci.* 32 (2006) 252–260. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clay.2006.02.005>.
- 609 [45] X. Cheng, X. Huang, X. Wang, D. Sun, Influence of calcination on the adsorptive removal of phosphate by Zn – Al
610 layered double hydroxides from excess sludge liquor, *J. Hazard. Mater.* 177 (2010) 516–523.
611 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2009.12.063>.
- 612 [46] F.L. Theiss, G.A. Ayoko, R.L. Frost, Thermogravimetric analysis of selected layered double hydroxides, *J. Therm. Anal.*
613 *Calorim.* 112 (2013) 649–657. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10973-012-2584-z>.
- 614 [47] M. Everaert, V. Lemmens, T.A. Atia, J. Spooren, Sulfidic mine tailings and marl waste rock as compatible resources in a
615 microwave-assisted roasting process, *J. Clean. Prod.* 274 (2020) 1–28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.122628>.
- 616 [48] H. Hatami, A. Fotovat, A. Halajnia, Comparison of adsorption and desorption of phosphate on synthesized Zn-Al LDH by
617 two methods in a simulated soil solution, *Appl. Clay Sci.* 152 (2018) 333–341.
618 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clay.2017.11.032>.
- 619 [49] M. Everaert, K. Slenders, K. Dox, S. Smolders, D. De Vos, E. Smolders, The isotopic exchangeability of phosphate in Mg-
620 Al layered double hydroxides, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 520 (2018) 25–32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcis.2018.03.010>.

621 [50] R.W. Blanchar, L.R. Hossner, Hydrolysis and Sorption of Ortho-, Pryo-, Tripoly-, and Trimetaphosphate in 32
622 Midwestern Soils, Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J. 33 (1969) 622–625.
623 <https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj1969.03615995003300040037x>.

624